

THE COMPARISON OF ADJECTIVES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Muydinov Bekzod

Master's degree student of Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7407898>

Abstract

English language is one of the widespread languages in the world and learning the language is implausible to envision without comparative analysis of grammar and vocabulary of the languages. This thesis is dedicated to elucidate the comparison of adjectives in Uzbek and English languages and their semantic features in the contexts.

Key words: adjective, morphology, affixation, degree, root.

Introduction

It is plain that languages can be distinguished in many ways. It may be used for different contents. Morphology is the general category that can be generally compared in both English and Uzbek languages. Morphology is the analysis of words, how they are formed, and their connection to other parts of speech in the same language. It studies the structure of words such as stems, root words, affixation. In the morphology, there are some distinct features of all parts of speech, particularly, adjectives.

Methods and materials

An adjective, in grammar, is a part of speech whose main syntactic role is to describe a noun or pronoun (called the adjective's subject), providing with more information about noun or pronoun. Generally, adjectives form one of the conventional eight parts of speech, though contemporary linguists differentiate adjectives from words such as determiners that used to be regarded adjectives but that are now considered as different part of speech in a language. An adjective is a part of speech that describes a noun or pronoun by providing descriptive or specific detail. Unlike adverbs, adjectives do not describe verbs but adjectives are connected to nouns and pronouns. Adjectives usually come before the noun or pronoun they describe. Adjectives do not have to agree in number or gender with the nouns they describe.

Results and discussion

An adjective is a part of speech that qualifies or describes a noun in both Uzbek and English

English:

Blue sky -
Yummy cake -
Fragrant flower -
Smart student -
Big stone -
Long thread -

Uzbek :

Moviy osmon
Mazali tort
Xushbo'y gul
Aqlli talaba
Katta tosh
Uzun ip

English adjectives: **il-/im-** /**in-/ir-**(illiterate), impossible, inadequate, irrelevant), **post-** (post- war), **pre-** (preliminary), **un-** (unnecessary), - **able/ible** (reliable, accessible), **-al**(natural), **-an/- ean /-ian** (American, Mediterranean, cyclopedian), **-ary** (revolutionary), **-ate** (elaborate) **-ed** (pointed), **-en** (golden), **-fold** (fivefold), **-ful** (forceful), **-ic** (scenic), **-ish** (reddish), **-ive** (adhesive), **-less**(homeless), **-like** (childlike), **-ly** (comely),- **most** (heedmost), **-tory / -ory** (explanatory,modulatory), **-ous** (ous), **-some** (troublesome), **-y** (shady), **-ical** (critical).

Uzbek adjectives: **ba-** (bahaybat), **be-** (beozor), **bo-** (boobro'), **no-** (noaniq), **bad-** (badbaxt),- **li** (totli), **-siz** (ishsiz), **-gi, -ki, -qi** (tonggi, chillaki,tashqi), **-dagi** (ruldagi), **-chan, / -chang** (ishchan, ko'ylakchang), **-chil** (epchil), **iy-** (nazariy), - **simon** (odamsimon), **-ik, / -iq, / -uq** (egik, qiyshiq, quruq), **-ma** (ezma), **-qoq / -g'oq** (tarqoq, toyg'oq), **-choq, / -chiq** (erinchoq, qizg'anchiq), **-kir, / -qir** (o'tkir, topqir), **-g'on** (bilag'on), **-iv** (intensiv), **-lik** (yillik), **-al** (aktual).

In both languages many nouns can function as nouns and as adjectives.

For example, English: poor, sick, unemployed, old, young, rich, disabled.

Uzbek: kambag'allar, kasallar ishizlar, keksalar, yoshlar, boy,nogironlar

There are 3 category degrees of adjectives in English language.

It is represented by the system of three-member opposition:

-positive;

-comparative;

-superlative degrees.

The positive degree is morphologically unmarked. It is the primary form of the adjective and it expresses simple quality if the thing or the person expressed by the

subject is not compared with anything:

*David is a **smart** boy.*

things compared:

*David is as **clever** as Mike.*

*She is **beautiful**.*

*David is as **stupid** as Mike.*

The comparative degree is morphologically marked in both languages. In English it expresses a higher or less degree of quality of the thing expressed by the subject related to the item with which it is compared. Depending on the length of the adjective it is made by two ways:

1) by adding the suffix **-er** to short adjectives: *big-bigger, cold-colder* etc.

2) by adding the words more or less before long adjectives:
essential - more essential comfortable - more comfortable

In Uzbek it is formed by adding the suffix **-roq** to the adjective: *katta - kattaroq*

The affix **-roq** means **a (little) bit more** or **a (little) bit less**:

Bobur Dianadan aqlliroq - Bobur is smarter than Diana

The superlative degree expresses the highest (least) degree of the quality meant by the adjective stem with the affix **-est** and the structures **most + adj**

Smart + est - smartest

most + careful - the most careful

In Uzbek language, superlative form of adjective is formed by using word **eng** before adjective.

Eng muhim - the most important

eng yangi - the newest

In conclusion, there can be seen a few similarities in the grammatical and morphological features of adjectives in both Uzbek and English language, particularly in the formation and degree categories

References:

1. Dixon R.M.W.1999. Adjectives. In K.Brown & T.Miller (eds.), Concise Encyclopedia of Grammatical Categories. Amsterdam.
2. Смирницкий А.И. 1959. Морфология английского языка. Москва.
3. M.I.Rasulova, Z.I.Shukurova.2017. Comparative typology of English, Uzbek and Russian languages. Tashkent.
4. Yusupov U'. Constrastive linguistics of the English and Uzbek languages. Akadernashr, Toshkent, 2013, 280p
5. Zokirov, M., & Isomiddinov, F. (2020). December. ABOUT THE HOLES OF LANGUAGE LANGUAGE DICTIONARY. Конференции.

